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DATA LINK CONTROL AND PROTOCOLS

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Abstract: *The field of data communication relies on effective data link control and protocols to ensure reliable and secure information exchange between connected devices. Data Link Control (DLC) mechanisms play a crucial role in managing the flow of data across communication channels, addressing issues such as error detection, flow control, and framing. Protocols, on the other hand, establish the rules and conventions that govern the format and sequence of messages exchanged between devices. They define the procedures for initiating, maintaining, and terminating communication sessions. Additionally, as we navigate the complexities of modern networks, understanding and implementing effective DLC and protocol strategies become paramount for ensuring the reliability and security of data exchanges.*

Keywords: *Data, flow Control, transmitting, error, retransmission.*

INTRODUCTION

Data – link layer is responsible for implementation of point-to-point flow and error control mechanism.

Flow Control – When a data frame (Layer-2 data) is sent from one host to another over a single medium, it is required that the sender and receiver should work at the same speed. That is, sender sends at a speed on which the receiver can process and accept the data. What if the speed (hardware/software) of the sender

or receiver differs? If sender is sending too fast the receiver may be overloaded, (swamped) and data may be lost.

Two types of mechanisms can be deployed to control the flow:

Stop and Wait – This flow control mechanism forces the sender after transmitting a data frame to stop and wait until the acknowledgement of the data-frame sent is received.

Sliding Window

In this flow control mechanism, both sender and receiver agree on the number of data-frames after which the acknowledgement should be sent. As we learnt, stop and wait flow control mechanism wastes resources, this protocol tries to make use of underlying resources as much as possible.

Error Control – When data-frame is transmitted, there is a probability that data-frame may be lost in the transit or it is received corrupted. In both cases, the receiver does not receive the correct data-frame and sender does not know anything about any loss. In such case, both sender and receiver are equipped with some protocols which helps them to detect transit errors such as loss of data-frame. Hence, either the sender retransmits the data-frame or the receiver may request to resend the previous data frame. Requirements for error control mechanism:

- Error detection: The sender and receiver, either both or any, must ascertain that there is some error in the transit.
- Positive ACK: When the receiver receives a correct frame, it should acknowledge it.
- Negative ACK: When the receiver receives a damaged frame or a duplicate frame, it sends a NACK back to the sender and the sender must retransmit the correct frame.

– Retransmission: The sender maintains a clock and sets a timeout period. If an acknowledgement of a data-frame previously transmitted does not arrive before the timeout, the sender retransmits the frame, thinking that the frame or its acknowledgement is lost in transit.

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